

Q2. What challenges do you experience in data collection for risk analysis?

55 Answers

Mentimeter

I'm in the field of developing new methods to identify microplastics and speed up the risk assessment process. The data on MNP specific "fingerprints" of the diff. analysis methods is limited.

Lack of harmonized methods and procedures for MPs analysis and risk assessment

Difficult to maintain biological sample quality due to lot of anthropogenic contaminations in sampling areas.

no acknowledged guidelines, no harmonization, no standardization

lack of standardization

not correctly formatted data

To isolate copepods by traditional methods is very challenging, Advanced and modern microscopes are not available in my laboratory to identify nanoplastic in zooplankton.

Try to search in ECHA website

Dat format

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Good characterization of reference material, lack of RM MNPs

Data quality

Lack of data

Reduction of data needs

Poor QA/QC practises

Unstandardised sampling and analysis methods of MNPs

Scattered data, rush to collect them

Harmonized toxicity data

Relevant models

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relevant plastics

relevant concentrations

Lack of standardized monitoring method

Convince-help researchers to use same templates and SOPs

A bias in PS-NMPs which do not actually represent the biggest contributor to environmental and human exposure

Appropriate characterization of complex exposure

data scarcity

Information on polydisperse plastics

The lack of common definitions for MNPLs in general.

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In soils, representative sampling of samples for analysis to obtain sufficient results is difficult.

To find reliable data on the plastics used in the experiments.

The reliability of data reported in open literature

Although I am new in the field, the big challenge for me is to obtain the reliable test material to study impact of micro/nanoplastics on airway cell systems including 3D organoids from patient groups

no data available, conflicting results

Finding correlations between multivariables at different stages of experiments

Not to go in detail any more, but to select an extreme minimum of relevant data

Lack of data on materials other than PS

Lack of standardisation or agreement in which hazards/hypothesis's need to be tested

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standardization of the collected data

data are not annotated with sufficient metadata to be reusable

Insufficient characterisation of tested materials

The huge number plastic of additives making it a very complex task to get an overview and to make a system for assessment.

The large diversity in micro- and nanoplastic with regard to both physical and chemical properties, as well as biological components bound to them.

Reliability and comparability Environmental relevance (Media, organisms, long-term data) Realistic exposure scenarios (Release from articles/products, Mixtures, Transformation of particles)

lack of harmonized data reporting templates

No point of departure or biological effect level from most studies, cannot be used in risk assessment

In soil sample analysis, it is difficult to perform representative sampling of samples for analysis to obtain sufficient results. That is, an innovative method for maximizing the sampling amount is re

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Lab experiments: where do you get different material (not only pristine particles) to perform tests?

There are no fixed protocols to collect and compare data

Lack of validated methods to determine occurrence of MNPs in the various compartments. lack of agreed definition on micro-nanoplasticslack of agreed data requirements for risk analysis

MNP load, MNP delivery to target organ tissue, coeffects of other biotic and abiotic agents with MNPs

Toxicity data

Comparable and reproducible data Environmental relevant data (Media, organisms, long term)Realistic exposure scenarios (Release from products/articles, Transformation of particles, Mixture effects)

Access to free, high quality and curated data is limited.

We have collected samples of MNPs in the rivers of a Galicia (Spain) region. Because there were no available data on MNPs contamination in the area, the collection was mandatory.

Lack of quality standards and of procedures for sharing data

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Format to be used

Q3. Please select the most urgent problem in the data collection for risk analysis Mentimeter

Q4. What tasks/research questions are needed for future projects

22 Answers

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Test method for NPs/MPs in human real samples

Quantifying human exposure to microplastics from the environment, to enable a risk assessment to be conducted

Development of protocols to assess the degradation level of the micro and nanoplastics.

NP detection methods

More human data parameters (health effects) such as metabolomics/proteomics data or OLINK data due to exposure to MNPs.

complete and harmonized reporting of experiments, measurements, materials

Availability of certified reference materials of a wide variety of plastic types and size classes

Nanoplastics analysis

I need to see well characterized and reliable materials for testing these in more reliable 3D organic models.

Q4. What tasks/research questions are needed for future projects

22 Answers

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Exposure measurement of MNP in real scenarios

Microplastics in human health

The interplay between functional groups on the surface of weathered NMPs and their influence on toxicity.

How can we contribute to closing the Gender Data Gap (the fact that the standard for most data collection is the white man) when working on collecting data for human health risk assessment of MNPLs?

microplastics in human health

Realistic scenarios (Hazard and exposure)

sorry I mean 3D organoid models

test a larger variety of polymers

Harmonize protocols from the current running projects and continuation/finalization of standardization

Q4. What tasks/research questions are needed for future projects

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microplastics in human health, nano plastics in human tissues, MPs/NPs in environment

"Transfer" of data from personal computers and lab computers into structures format ready for sharing and reuse

Realistic scenarios (Hazard and exposure)

Realistic scenarios (Hazard and exposure)